

Supporting Schema and Data Provenance under Database Evolution with PROV Template

–Supplementary Material–

Introduction

This document contains the supplementary material for the PROV-Interoperable Database Evolution Approach (PROV-IDEA), which has been organized as follows:

- Section 1 Process for specifying a PROV template for an SMO
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1 Process for specifying a PROV template for an SMO

The specification of the PROV template for an SMO is performed following five steps, which guide us through the elements and relations that must be taken into account to obtain the final template. The *first step* is a preliminary step in which the formal semantics of the SMO is considered, to establish the involved elements, as well as the provenance that must be collected and that will guide the rest of steps. The following four steps (steps 2 to 5) are in charge of generating the specification of the PROV template.

An excerpt of the actions performed in steps 2 to 5 of the template specification process is shown in Figure 1. Firstly, the input and output elements of the process are indicated. In particular, the input of the process includes the considered SMO, the input and output parameters of the SMO, the elements involved in the modifications performed in the database (added and deleted elements) and, where appropriate, the SMOs/DMOs into which the SMO being considered is decomposed. As a result, the template obtained from the execution of the steps is the final output.

During the *second step*, a fixed set of elements and relations that are part of all the templates are included. Specifically, the agent performing the operation and the SMO executed are specified. Furthermore, the source schema, to which the SMO is applied, and the target schema, generated from the execution of the SMO, together with their associated elements are included in the template.

The input parameters used by the SMO and the output parameters generated by the SMO are specified in the *third step*. Besides, when the output parameter is a table, its columns and values are also included.

The modifications performed by the SMO are specified during the *fourth step*. When a table is added, it is specified as a member of the target schema, together with its elements derived from the corresponding source elements. In addition, it may be necessary to add other relations specific to the SMO semantics. Besides, when an element is deleted, the invalidation of this element is included in the template.

Finally, in the *fifth step*, if the SMO is a composition of other SMOs/DMOs, then these operations are included as activities informed by the SMO being specified.

As an example of the application of this process, the textual specification of the PROV template corresponding to the COPY TABLE schema operation appears in Figure 2. In this figure, the elements and relations generated by each step have been separated into different blocks.

2 PROV-IDEA Templates

The PROV templates obtained as a result of applying the process explained in the previous section have been rigorously described by means of a pattern-based structure. This structure consists of six blocks: *Identifier* assigning a unique acronym to each SMO/DMO; *Syntax*, that states the SQL-like syntax of the

```

Input: smo, input parameters, output parameters,
        added tables with elements, deleted elements,
        affected operations
Output: template T
Process:
//Step 2: 'where' and 'why shallow' related information
include in T element agent(var:user)
include in T element activity(var:smo, <attrs>)
include in T relation wasAssociatedWith(var:smo, var:user,-)
include in T element entity(var:sourceSchema, <attrs>)
include in T relation wasInvalidatedBy(var:sourceSchema, var:smo,-)
include in T element entity(var:targetSchema, <attrs>)
include in T relation wasGeneratedBy(var:targetSchema, var:smo,-)
include in T relation wasDerivedFrom(var:targetSchema, var:sourceSchema,-,-,-)
include in T element entity(var:previousTable, <attrs>)
include in T relation hadMember(var:targetSchema, var:previousTable)
//Step 3: 'how' related information
For each input parameter i do
    include in T element entity(var:i, <attrs>)
    include in T relation used(var:smo, var:i,-)
For each output parameter o do
    include in T element entity(var:o, <attrs>)
    include in T relation wasGeneratedBy(var:o, var:smo,-)
    If o is a table then
        include in T relation hadMember(var:o, var:<column>)
        include in T relation specializationOf(var:<value>, var:<column>)
//Step 4: 'how' related information
For each added table t do
    include in T relation hadMember(var:targetSchema, var:t)
    For each element e of t do
        include in T relation wasDerivedFrom(var:e, var:<sourceElement>,-,-,-)
        include in T elements and relations <specific of the added semantics>
For each deleted element d do
    include in T relation wasInvalidatedBy(var:d, var:smo,-)
//Step 5: 'why deep' related information
For each affected operation ao do
    include in T element activity(var:ao, <attrs>)
    include in T relation wasInformedBy(var:ao, var:smo)

```

Fig. 1. Excerpt of the PROV template specification process

SMO/DMO pattern (in the case of SMOs, we have mainly based on the syntax given in [1]); *Semantics* expressing the effect of the application of the SMO/DMO in the database, including a description of the key elements; *SMO/DMO's involved elements*, that contains the elements that model the key elements of the SMO/DMO semantics; *Mapping to PROV*, that corresponds to the PROV template proposed from the previous SMO/DMO's involved elements; and *Discussion*, that presents issues related to the representation of the SMOs/DMOs with PROV.

The proposed specification structure facilitates their understandability and maintenance, enabling other researchers to replicate the presented proposal. Concretely, we have specified 6 SMO patterns (CREATE TABLE, DROP TABLE, ADD COLUMN, COPY TABLE, MERGE TABLE and DECOMPOSE TABLE) and 2 DMO patterns (INSERT and DELETE). We note that our intention is not to define patterns

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<pre>agent(var:user) activity(var:smo, -, -, [o2p:instruction='var:operationInstruction', o2p:exec wasAssociatedWith(var:smo, var:user, -) entity(var:sourceSchema, [sch2p:schemaName='var:sSchemaName', prov:type='sch2 wasInvalidatedBy(var:sourceSchema, var:smo, -) entity(var:targetSchema, [sch2p:schemaName='var:tShemaName', bitemp:startVali wasGeneratedBy(var:targetSchema, var:smo, -) wasDerivedFrom(var:targetSchema, var:sourceSchema, -, -, -) entity(var:previousTable, [sch2p:tableName='var:pTableName', prov:type='sch2p hadMember(var:targetSchema, var:previousTable)</pre>	Schema change
<pre>entity(var:sourceTable, [sch2p:tableName='var:sTableName', prov:type='sch2p:t used(var:smo, var:sourceTable, -) entity(var:targetTableName, [prov:value='var:inTableName']) used(var:smo, var:targetTableName, -)</pre>	Input parameters
<pre>entity(var:targetTable, [sch2p:tableName='var:tTableName', bitemp:startValidT wasGeneratedBy(var:targetTable, var:smo, -) entity(var:targetColumn, [sch2p:columnName='var:tColumnName', tpl:linked='va wasGeneratedBy(var:targetColumn, var:smo, -) entity(var:targetColumnValue, [d2p:rowID='var:tRowId', tpl:linked='var:sourc wasGeneratedBy(var:targetColumnValue, var:smo, -) hadMember(var:targetTable, var:targetColumn) specializationOf(var:targetColumnValue, var:targetColumn)</pre>	Output parameters
<pre>hadMember(var:targetSchema, var:targetTable) wasDerivedFrom(var:targetTable, var:targetTableName, -, -, -) wasDerivedFrom(var:targetTable, var:sourceTable, -, -, -) entity(var:sourceColumn, [sch2p:columnName='var:sColumnName', prov:type='sch2 wasDerivedFrom(var:targetColumn, var:sourceColumn, -, -, -) entity(var:sourceColumnValue, [d2p:rowID='var:sRowId', prov:type='d2p:value', wasDerivedFrom(var:targetColumnValue, var:sourceColumnValue, -, -, -)</pre>	Evolution process
<pre>activity(var:smoCT, -, -, [o2p:instruction='var:ctOperationInstruction', o2p: wasInformedBy(var:smoCT, var:smo) activity(var:dmoI, -, -, [o2p:instruction='var:iOperationInstruction', o2p:ex wasInformedBy(var:dmoI, var:smo)</pre>	Related SMO/DMO

Fig. 2. Textual specification of the COPY TABLE PROV template

for all the schema evolution operators, but focusing on those we have considered of more interest for provenance purposes and for evaluating the feasibility of the proposal.

We do not include the specification of the PROV templates in this document for space reasons, but their complete specification can be consulted in [2].

3 Implementation details

Aimed at establishing a reference implementation for the *PROV-IDEA module*, we have based on the characteristics presented in [3,4] for the implementation of the module that captures provenance (named Bindings Generation Module or *BGM*) to make applications provenance-aware. The implementation reference we propose for the *PROV-IDEA module* is mainly based upon an event-based design that identifies two main elements: *events*, which are notable occurrences

that happen while the application is running, and *listeners*, which specify the behaviour for processing the events. This distinction allows decoupling provenance capture from the actual generation of provenance data, so that a same schema evolution application can have simultaneously several listeners, each managing provenance in a different way. In this context, different aspects can be considered such as bindings storage or provenance computation (that is, when to expand the final PROV documents). More specifically, bindings can be stored in different storage systems (e.g., file systems, relational databases or NoSQL systems), serialized in a more or less verbose format (e.g., JSON, TURTLE, etc.), or being persisted in different forms (individually or as sets of bindings, or even as expanded PROV documents). Considering the two main strategies generally used by provenance systems to decide when to compute the final provenance data [5] (either when it is required, usually referred to as *lazy*, or immediately, *eager*) this strategy is agnostic about when to compute the final PROV documents, giving freedom to PROV-IDEA software developers to choose between following a *lazy* or an *eager* approach when implementing listeners. Thus, this event-based design facilitates decision making on all these aspects. For example a provenance consumer may be interested in directly obtaining provenance documents for immediate consumption including only evolution information at a particular level of granularity (i.e. only schema evolution but not data changes). For the remaining data, he may want to store the bindings information, perhaps in a secondary storage system, just for possible future queries. This different processing would only require the development of two listeners, thus providing a modular solution.

Our event-design is materialised in an architecture that relies on four elements, which we organise in three packages (see Figure 3). The *BGMEventInstrumenter* class, included in the *instrumenter* package, recognises the execution of SMOs/DMOs in the instrumented application, and consequently triggers events, generating instances of the *BGMEvent* class in the *events* package. Objects of this class carry information about the occurrence of events and encapsulate the data provenance regarding the evolution schema and/or data changes needed for constructing the corresponding bindings. These events are captured by *listeners*, that is, classes that implement the *BGMEventListener* interface. PROV-IDEA software developers can implement this interface according their preferred strategy for computing provenance, that is, for generating, managing, and storing the bindings data carried by the *BGMEvents*. Since the proposal allows using several listeners, the helper class, *BGMEventManager* is used to manage the list of subscribed listeners, and disseminate the *BGMEvent* objects among them as events occur (both the *BGMEventListener*, and *BGMEventManager* are included in the *listeners* package as it is shown in Figure 3). Taking this into account, our event-design proposal is composed of *application-independent* components (which correspond to the *events* package, with the *BGMEvent* class, and the *listeners* package, with the *BGMEventListener* interface and the *BGMEventManager* class) and the *application-dependent* component (which correspond to the *instrumenter* package, with the single element *BGMEventInstrumenter* class).

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Fig. 3. The PROV-IDEA approach applied to QuantumDB tool

4 Proof of Concept

As proof of concept, we have applied our proposal to QuantumDB [6,7,8], an open source Java tool designed to execute database schema migrations on SQL databases with zero-downtime, that is, without exhibiting blocking behavior during evolving databases (for example, table locks set when performing changes). QuantumDB was chosen for several reasons. First, given the difficulty of finding a functional and available tool that supports not only schema evolution but also versioning DML statements (such as inserting, updating and deleting records), we have chosen QuantumDB among other schema evolution tools since it tracks finer grained data, so that we can compare and place value on the provenance generated by PROV-IDEA. In contrast to other versioning database schema tools, such as Liquibase or Flyway, that just track executed changesets (i.e., series of schema changes) in a special metadata table in the same database, QuantumDB provides a more complex schema evolution strategy, tracking also how every table and column evolves over time through these operations, as well as what transformations they undergo. Second, while not being strictly SMOs-based, QuantumDB allows users to define their changes in sets of operations which belong to each other and need to be executed together in a particular sequence [6]. Thus, it gives us the flexibility to simulate SMOs/DMOs operators. Third, QuantumDB’s source code is freely available at a GitHub repository [8], which allows us to go deep into the code and get familiar with it, task needed to develop the *PROV-IDEA module*. Fourth, we have direct contact with its developers, who can provide us with useful additional background about the tool and can assist us to assess the quality of the provenance generated by PROV-IDEA. Fifth, QuantumDB lacks a development strategy that ensures an easy and straightforward development of the *PROV-IDEA module*, using the AOP

paradigm. More specifically, our AOP-based proposal for the development of the module captures the provenance data by relying on the data gathered directly or indirectly from the values passed into or returned from the operations executed as the schema evolution application runs. The more information enclosed in the parameters of the operations in charge of executing SMOs/DMOS in an schema evolution application, the easier it is the development of its module. QuantumDB, for its part, does not fit well with this design scheme, thus, we are considering a complex case of application of *PROV-IDEA*, illustrating the effort that it may require, and offering a realistic vision of what applying *PROV-IDEA* can entail for applications whose development strategy does not fit well with the described favourable scenario. Last but not least, this tool has been compared extensively with other 11 schema migration tools against a list of four criteria concerning *functional*, *correctness*, *performance* and *tolerance of errors* aspects, concluding that QuantumDB stood out from the rest, scoring highest in the list of criteria [9].

4.1 *QuantumDB's way of working and architecture*

QuantumDB, like a lot of other schema evolution tools, allows users to define their changes in sets of operations, referred to as *changesets*. It tracks the database schema in a linear manner historically, where each operation in a changeset yields a new version of the database schema and each change set can be identified by the final resulting version of that change set [6]. In QuantumDB users have two methods to manage databases, providing such change sets either in Java code, by using the *QuantumDB API*, or in a changelog XML file named `changelog.xml`, by using the command line interface given by the QuantumDB CLI tool. In this proof of concept we have decided to use this latter method for being the recommended and easiest option to manage databases with QuantumDB, as stated in [6] (see Figure 3).

QuantumDB consists of five components (see Figure 3), each performing their own task. The *cli* component contains specific classes to process the XML code in the changesets and perform migrations using commands on the command line interface. The *core* component contains the main logic and ontology classes that represent the database structure and provide the zero-downtime schema migration used to power QuantumDB. Such a zero-downtime schema migration ability is achieved by providing a *mixed state* for every schema changeset which, at the same time, is obtained by automatically maintaining a set of synchronised “ghost tables” for those tables affected (either directly or indirectly) by the changes. The *driver* component, also know as the *QuantumDB-driver*, is a small Java library which implements all required classes to act like a JDBC driver. It is in charge of intercepting queries being issued to the database and, before handing them to the actual JDBC driver, it alters the queries both by specifying on which version of the database schema the *core* code should be operating on and rewriting the query replacing the table names present in that query with the associated ghost table IDs for that specific version. For this latter task, the *query-rewriter* component is used. QuantumDB presently supports PostgreSQL, yet it has been

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designed to be easily extensible to alternative relational database management systems (RDMS). More specifically, the current implementation includes the *PostgreSQL* component with the corresponding code needed to operate on a real PostgreSQL database.

4.2 PROV-IDEA module development

Firstly, we note that, to implement the module for the QuantumDB application, we have considered the systematic evaluation made to implement the *BGM* in [3,4] and adopted those characteristics that demonstrated clear advantages for the capture of provenance regarding aspects such as the instrumentation mode, run-time and storage overhead.

Regarding the *application-dependent* component, the *BGMEventInstrumenter* (see Figure 3) must be able to identify the places where the application’s operations in charge of executing SMOs/DMOs are invoked (that is, those places where *BGMEvent* objects have to be fired). Thus, making an application provenance-aware with our event-based approach would result in additional instructions scattered across all the application’s source code, needed to construct such events with the provenance data, and to disseminate them among the *BGMEventListeners*, by means of the *BGMEventManager*. This fact would require a developer to traverse the whole code to include such instructions, which would be tedious and error-prone, making the application maintenance a cumbersome task. Against this background, we rely on the Aspect-Oriented Programming (AOP) paradigm [10] to implement the *BGMEventInstrumenter*, which allows us to place provenance capture instructions apart from the application’s source code. More specifically, AOP allows a developer to modularize crosscutting concerns (such as logging, security or, in this case, provenance capture) into entities called *aspects*, which can then be “woven into” the core code by an *aspect weaver*, building the final system. This allows us to provide a non-intrusive instrumentation of schema evolution applications. By using this paradigm, we are able to recognize the occurrence of certain circumstances during the execution of the instrumented application (mainly the start and end of SMOs/DMOs operations), and consequently cause the execution of additional provenance capture instructions.

As described previously, the *core* component contains the main logic and ontology classes that represent the database structure. Such logic classes provide us with a basis to identify when SMOs/DMOs operations are executed and to be able to gather the provenance data to be captured, either directly or after performing some preprocessing of data. However, the implementation strategy of SMOs and DMOs differs so that while each SMO is encapsulated by an independent Java class in charge of implementing the core logic of the SMO, thus making it easier for us to gather the data to be captured; DMOs are executed by a general Java method that directly sends the SQL statement to the database to be executed, which requires an extra effort to extract the database elements (such as tables, columns or rows) involved in the SQL statement. As advanced, the provenance capture instructions are included in the *BGMEventInstrumenter*

component which, given that QuantumDB is implemented in Java, we have developed using AspectJ, an AOP extension created for Java. More specifically, we have implemented the *BGMEventInstrumenter* by means of an *aspect*, which is made up of specific *pointcuts* and two *advices* of type before and after, respectively (see Figure 4).

In order to support our explanations regarding the implementation of the *BGMEventInstrumenter*, we will use as an example the implementation of the COPY TABLE SMO, for being one of the most complex SMO supported by this application. In particular, since this SMO is decomposed into the CREATE TABLE SMO and the INSERT DMO, we thus give support to a complete set of related SMOs/DMOs. Taking this into account, a *pointcut* has been defined per each considered SMO to capture its execution while, given the previous explanation, we have created an only *pointcut* to capture the execution of any DMO operation (the INSERT operation, in this case). As a way of example, in the *pointcut* named `copyTableToPROV` (see lines 4 and 5 on the left hand side of Figure 4), the identified operation execution corresponds to the method `migrate` of class `CopyTableMigrate`, in charge of migrating the database to the evolved state, which ensures us that the SMO has been performed. Since the events can occur both before and after operation executions, we have used both a *before* and an *after advice* associated to the defined *pointcuts* to specify the custom behaviour to be executed before and after the actual behaviour. More specifically, the main idea behind the *before advice* is performing two steps (see lines from 9 to 19 on the left hand side of Figure 4). First, it gathers provenance data common to all SMOs/DMOs (such as the operation execution' start) obtained from the parameters passed into the executed operation captured by the *pointcut*, either directly or after performing some preprocessing. Second, it finally constructs suitable `BGMEvent` objects that capture such data and disseminate them to the *BGMEventListeners* (by invoking the `disseminateEvent` operation of the `BGMEventManager`). In the case of the *after advice* (see lines from 20 to 30 on the left hand side of Figure 4), it identifies the kind of the executed operation (that is, a concrete SMO or a DMO) and gathers preliminary key data from the parameters passed into the executed operation (see lines from 24 to 26 on the left hand side of Figure 4) so that they can be passed into concrete auxiliary methods that finally capture provenance data concerning the executed SMO/DMO. These auxiliary methods act similarly to the *before advice* in the sense that they mainly gather provenance data and construct suitable `BGMEvent` objects that capture such data and disseminate them to the listeners. More specifically, we have implemented an auxiliary method for each considered operator, where the method implementing the COPY TABLE SMO (see the `copyToPROV` on the right hand side of Figure 4) not only captures provenance data related to the execution of the operator itself, but also invokes the auxiliary methods implementing the CREATE TABLE SMO and the INSERT DMO (see lines 4 and 6) in order to finally capture the overall provenance data. As a result, the developed *aspect* has been defined so that it collects both schema and data provenance information considering the structure of the defined PROV templates and the variables

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```

Excerpt of the BGMEventInstrumenter
1 @Aspect
2 public class BGMEventInstrumenter {
3     (this pointcut identifies the migration of the copy table operation)
4     @Pointcut("executed(* io.quantumdb.core.migration.operations.* CopyTableMigrator.migrate(..)")
5     CopyTableMigrator.migrate(..)")
6     public void copyTableToPROV() {}
7     [-]
8
9     @Before("copyTableToPROV || createTableToPROV() || DMOToPROV()")
10    public void captureStartData(JoinPoint joinPoint) {
11        // IDENTIFY PROVENANCE DATA known before the captured operators' execution itself
12        [-]
13    }
14    // CONSTRUCT SUITABLE BGMEvent OBJECTS that capture the previous identified data and DISSEMINATE them to the listener
15    BGMEvent operationStart = new BGMEvent(-);
16    bgmEM.disseminateEvent("OperationStart", operationStart);
17    [-]
18
19    @After("copyTableToPROV() || createTableToPROV() || DMOToPROV()")
20    public void captureRemainderData(JoinPoint joinPoint) {
21        [-]
22    }
23    Object[] signatureArgs = joinPoint.getArgs();
24    for (Object signatureArg : signatureArgs) {
25        // Identify the executed operation and key data
26        [-]
27    }
28    if(operation.equalsIgnoreCase("CopyTable"))
29        copyToPROV(-); //Method that captures copy table provenance data
30    } else if(-){
31        [-]
32    }
33
Excerpt of QuantumDB core package code
1 package io.quantumdb.core.migration.operations;
2 [-]
3 class CopyTableMigrator implements
4     SchemaOperationMigrator<CopyTable>{
5     [-]
6     public void migrate(Catalog catalog, RefLog refLog,
7         Version version, CopyTable operation){
8     [-]
9     [-] //Method's content
10    }
11    }
12
Excerpt of copyToProv method
1 public void copyToPROV (Version sourceSchVers, Version targetSchVers,
2     TableRef sourceTableRef, TableRef targetTableRef,...){
3     [-]
4     createToPROV (-); //Method that captures create table provenance data
5     DMOToPROV (-); //Method that captures insert rows DMO provenance data
6     [-]
7     //IDENTIFY PROVENANCE DATA concerning the copy table operation itself
8     [-]
9     //CONSTRUCT SUITABLE BGMEvent OBJECTS and DISSEMINATE them
10    [-]
11    BGMEvent operationEnd = new BGMEvent(-);
12    bgmEM.disseminateEvent("OperationEnd", operationEnd);
13    [-]
14    }
15    }

```

Fig. 4. Structure overview of the BGMEventInstrumenter in AspectJ

included in the bindings corresponding to those in the templates. Finally, the AspectJ *weaver* automatically integrates the custom behaviour from the aspect into the locations specified by the *pointcuts* at compilation time. In this way, our AOP approach does not require a manual intervention to adapt the source code, collecting provenance data in an automatic and transparent for software developers way.

Regarding the *application-independent* component, we note that we have developed a listener, named as for the `SetBindingsListener`, which performs an asynchronous recording, in which bindings are accumulated in memory before being shipped, as sets of bindings, to a MongoDB database (serialised in TURTLE format) after finishing the execution of each operation. As concluded in [3], the chosen strategy yields less run-time overhead and a more compact storage than other strategies that store the bindings one by one (each requiring a database operation), or store directly the PROV documents (which entails storing extra topological information).

For more information, the QuantumDB code enriched with the PROV-IDEA module is publicly available from the GitHub repository at [11].

5 PROV-IDEA Expander

The *PROV-IDEA Expander* allows the interested user to obtain PROV documents from bindings with schema evolution provenance data, as established by the PROV-IDEA approach.

More specifically, this tool goes through the binding documents generated from the execution of schema evolution operations (both SMOs and DMOs), finds the PROV template related to each binding (that is, to each operation),

and, finally, uses the *expansion algorithm* [12] to generate the corresponding PROV document ready for provenance consumption.

The *PROV-IDEA Expander* is publicly accessible from the GitHub repository at [13].

6 PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector

The *PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector* allows the interested user to query provenance data in TURTLE format using the different SPARQL query forms, that is, `SELECT`, `DESCRIBE`, `CONSTRUCT`, and `ASK` [14]. In particular, the tool is expected to be used with the PROV documents generated by the *PROV-IDEA Expander*.

The tool provides three panels. The top panel includes several radio buttons (one per each SPARQL query form), together with a ‘Run’ button to execute the desired query. The query would have to be typed in the left panel, so that, once executed the query, the right panel would display the result, either in table format (`SELECT` queries) or in PROV graphic format (`DESCRIBE`, `CONSTRUCT`, and `ASK`). For example, the table form (`SELECT`) can be chosen to obtain concrete, independent values (such as database table, columns, or schema names). `DESCRIBE` and `CONSTRUCT` query forms can be used when looking for a more structured answer (such as the complete description of an SMO, including its specific attributes as established in the templates, together with the information of their associations with other entities). `ASK` query forms, on their part, can be used when interested in answering true/false questions (in this case, the tool shows the result as a simple PROV graph with a `true/false` value).

As an example, Figure 5 shows the *PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector*’s interface with the graphic PROV representation of the result obtained from the execution of a `CONSTRUCT` form query. The query, shown in the left panel, asks for the main characteristics of both the last SMO (the SMO and, if applicable, the involved DMO into which it is decomposed) used to generate a concrete surname value (in the query, the “ZaccheriaSN” surname) of a developer included in table `developer_sub_a` and the user who has executed such an operation. The result, represented by a graphic PROV representation (see the right panel), shows the main attributes of the involved operators (the *DECOMPOSE Table* SMO and its associated *INSERT* DMO), including their relation with the user who executed the operation (*Michael*).

The *PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector* is publicly accessible from the GitHub repository at [15].

7 Provenance consumption

PROV-IDEA has been evaluated using qualitative and quantitative arguments to show the benefits and trade-offs of applying PROV-IDEA for both provenance consumers and software engineers seeking to make their schema evolution applications provenance-aware.

7. PROVENANCE CONSUMPTION

Fig. 5. Interface of the PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector

In the particular case of the qualitative evaluation, we have defined a concrete list of questions about Why, How, Where, and When-provenance, with different levels of complexity in order to show that the generated provenance is detailed enough to answer such types of questions.

For space reasons, we do not include the list of questions in this document, but their definition, together with the corresponding answers, are available in [2].

References

1. Herrmann, K., Voigt, H., Behrend, A., Lehner, W.: Codel - A relationally complete language for database evolution. In: Proceedings of the 19th East European Conference of Advances in Databases and Information Systems -, ADBIS 2015. Volume 9282 of Lecture Notes in Computer Science., Springer (2015) 63–76
2. PROV-IDEA: Supplementary material (2024) Online at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6380742>. Last accessed July 11, 2024.
3. Sáenz-Adán, C., García-Izquierdo, Francisco J. Pérez, B., Huynh, T.D., Moreau, L.: Automated and non-intrusive provenance capture with UML2PROV. Computing (2021)
4. Sáenz-Adán, C., Pérez, B., García-Izquierdo, F.J., Moreau, L.: Integrating provenance capture and UML with UML2PROV: Principles and experience. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering **48**(1) (2022) 53–68

5. Pérez, B., Sáenz-Adán, C., Rubio, J.: A systematic review of provenance systems. *Knowledge and Information Systems* **57**(3) (2018) 495–543
6. QuantumDB: Available at <https://quantumdb.io/>. Last visited on July 11, 2024.
7. de Jong, M.: Zero-Downtime SQL Database Schema Evolution for Continuous Deployment. PhD thesis, Delft University of Technology (August 2015)
8. QuantumDB GitHub repository: Available at <https://github.com/quantumdb/quantumdb>. Last visited on July 11, 2024.
9. Richter, N.: Zero-downtime PostgreSQL database schema migrations in a continuous deployment environment at ING (October 2021) Business Information Technology MSc (60025). Available at <http://purl.utwente.nl/essays/88687>. Last visited on July 11, 2024.
10. Kiczales, G., Lamping, J., Mendhekar, A., Maeda, C., Lopes, C., Loingtier, J.M., Irwin, J.: Aspect-oriented programming. In: *Proceedings of the European Conference on Object-Oriented Programming (ECOOP'97)*, Berlin, Heidelberg (1997) 220–242
11. QuantumDB with PROV-IDEA. GitHub repository: (2022) Online at <https://github.com/PROV-IDEA/QuantumDBwithPROV-IDEA>. Last accessed July 11, 2024.
12. Moreau, L., Batlajery, B.V., Huynh, T.D., Michaelides, D., Packer, H.: A templating system to generate provenance. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* **44**(2) (2018) 103–121
13. PROV-IDEA Expander: (2024) Online at <https://github.com/PROV-IDEA/PROV-IDEA-Expander/>. Last accessed July 11, 2024.
14. SPARQL 1.1 Query Language: Available at <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>. Last visited on July 11, 2024.
15. PROV-IDEA Provenance Inspector: (2024) Online at <https://github.com/PROV-IDEA/PROV-IDEA-Provenance-Inspector/>. Last accessed July 11, 2024.